

Catalytic effect of CTAB reverse micelles on the reduction of methylene blue by ascorbic acid

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Abstract : The kinetics of the reduction of methylene blue (MB⁺) by ascorbic acid (HA⁻) has been studied in the presence of CTAB/CHCl₃/hexane/water reverse micelles. In the absence of acid, the reaction obeys simple first order kinetics with respect to both the reactants. The second order rate constant in the presence of reverse micelles, k_w (0.0360 mol⁻¹ dm³ s⁻¹) was found to be about sixty times greater than that of in aqueous medium, k_o (5.33×10^{-4} mol⁻¹ dm³ s⁻¹) under identical experimental conditions. The significant increase is attributed to (i) the concentration effect produced in the reverse micelles and (ii) lower micro polarity of the reverse micelles, which facilitates the reaction between oppositely charged ions. The effect of W ($= [H_2O]/[CTAB]$) at constant [CTAB] and variation of [CTAB] at fixed W has been studied. The kinetics at $W < 6$ is explained on the basis of special properties of the entrapped water while the kinetics at $W > 10$ is explained on the basis of ionic strength. The effect of [CTAB] on rate is also explained in terms of the binding of the reactants at the micellar interface as shown by the absorption spectra of methylene blue and ascorbic acid.

Keywords : Kinetics, methylene blue, ascorbic acid, water pool, CTAB reverse micelles.

Introduction

When surfactants aggregate in nonpolar solvents (forming reverse micelles) their polar or charged groups are located in the interior or core of the aggregate while their hydrocarbon tails extend into the bulk solvent. Thus, water is readily solubilised in the polar core, forming a water pool and this solubilised water exhibits peculiar properties characterised by a parameter $W = ([H_2O]/[Surfactant])^1$. At low water contents where $W \leq 5$, the water is structured due to interactions with the polar head groups and counter ions. When $W > 12$ unstructured 'free' water is appears and a water pool is formed. In the case of AOT [sodium bis(2-ethylhexyl)sulphosuccinate] reverse micelles, for $W \leq 6$, all water molecules are immobilised and only for $W > 12$ unstructured free water appears^{2,3}. The properties of these two clearly differentiated phases are different. For example, the structured water has comparatively lower dielectric constant, low mobility and a high ionic strength due to the counter ion in the case of

ionic surfactants. Also, since both hydrophilic and hydrophobic components are present, a variety of systems involving both types of substances can be studied. In our previous work, we have studied the aquation of tris-2,2'-bipyridyl iron(II), base hydrolysis of tris-1,10'-phenanthroline iron(II) and oxidation of iodide by V^V in the presence of CTAB reverse micelles⁴⁻⁶. In order to further investigate the influence of these unique properties of the water pools on kinetics of electron transfer reactions we have taken up the kinetic study of the reduction of methylene blue by ascorbic acid in the presence of CTAB reverse micelles.

The oxidation of ascorbic acid (which is a well known bio active reducing agent) to dehydro ascorbic acid has received a great deal of attention because of the important role the redox chemistry of ascorbic acid plays in human nutrition⁷. The kinetics of methylene blue-ascorbic acid reaction in the presence of CTAB, Triton X-100, SDS aqueous micelles was studied before⁸. In the present

paper, the influence of CTAB reverse micelles in the oxidation of ascorbic acid by methylene blue has been studied by changing the concentrations of CTAB and the W parameter. The results are reported.

Table 1. Effect of varying $[HA^-]$ on the observed rate constants (k_1)

$10^3 \times [HA^-]_0$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$W = 5.61$		$W = 15.0$	
	$10^2 \times [HA^-]_e$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^3 \times k_1$ (s ⁻¹)	$10^3 \times [HA^-]_e$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^3 \times k_1$ (s ⁻¹)
0.10	1.0	0.910	3.70	1.10
0.50	5.0	4.92	18.5	6.72
0.80	8.0	7.80	29.6	9.03
1.1	11	9.45	40.7	11.7
1.5	15	11.8	55.0	13.5
2.1	21	19.8	77.7	22.4
2.5	25	24.1	92.6	27.2

$[MB^+]_0 = 1.4 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm⁻³, $[CTAB]_0 = 0.1$ mol dm⁻³, $T = 29$ °C.

Results and discussion

The reaction between MB^+ and HA^- in CTAB/ $CHCl_3$ /hexane/water mixtures obeys first order kinetics with respect to MB^+ as observed by the linear plots between log of absorbance vs time, under the conditions, $\{[HA^-]_0 \gg [MB^+]_0\}$, 'o' signifying overall concentration with respect to the whole system. The pseudo-first order rate constant is directly proportional to $[HA^-]$ indicating first order kinetics with respect to the second reactant (Table 1) and the reaction mechanism is given in Scheme 1.

Effect of variation of W :

The second order rate constant, k_2 has been deter-

mined over a wide range of W (0.87 to 25.0) at constant $[CTAB]$ and has been repeated at different $[CTAB]$ (Table 2). At constant $[CTAB]$, k_2 increases with W , but

Table 2. Observed first order (k_1) and second order rate constants (k_2) for the reduction of methylene blue by ascorbic acid

$[CTAB]_0$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[Br^-]_e$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^3 \times f$ (volume fraction)	W (s ⁻¹)	$10^3 \times k_1$ (mol ⁻¹ dm ³ s ⁻¹)	$10^3 \times k_2$ (mol ⁻¹ dm ³ s ⁻¹)	
0.1	21.3	4.70	2.61	20.0	63.80	
	15.4	6.50	3.61	16.6	71.20	
	12.1	8.30	4.61	13.7	75.80	
	9.91	10.0	5.61	11.8	78.60	
	8.41	11.9	6.61	10.2	80.90	
	5.55	18.0	10.0	12.0	144.0	
	3.71	27.0	15.0	13.4	236.0	
	2.77	36.0	20.0	14.0	336.0	
	2.22	45.0	25.0	18.0	545.0	
	0.2	41.7	4.70	1.30	20.0	62.60
		21.3	9.40	2.61	16.0	100.3
		15.4	12.9	3.61	13.0	111.8
12.1		16.5	4.61	12.4	136.2	
9.91		20.2	5.61	10.5	141.3	
8.41		23.8	6.61	9.90	157.2	
5.55		36.0	10.0	12.1	288.0	
3.71		54.0	15.0	11.7	417.8	
2.77		72.0	20.0	13.9	668.2	
2.22		90.0	25.0	17.7	1041	
0.3		63.8	4.70	0.870	26.0	81.40
		41.7	7.20	1.30	23.0	110.4
	21.3	14.1	2.61	15.0	141.1	
	15.4	19.5	3.61	11.5	149.4	
	12.1	24.9	4.61	9.70	161.1	
	9.91	30.3	5.61	9.20	186.0	
	8.41	35.7	6.61	8.70	207.1	
	5.55	54.0	10.0	10.0	370.4	
	3.71	81.0	15.0	11.5	627.0	
	2.77	108	20.0	13.6	986.0	
	2.22	135	25.0	14.2	1290	

$[HA^-]_0 = 1.5 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³, $[MB^+]_0 = 1.4 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm⁻³, $T = 29$ °C.

in the range of $W = 0.87$ to 6.61 the increase in k_2 is much less compared to the increase in k_2 in the range 10.0 to 25.0. In the lower W range, the confined water is utilised to solvate the ionic surfactant head groups and counter ions and therefore the reaction can be considered to take place at the interface. The water is highly struc-

tured in this low W range and is associated with special properties like lower micro polarity. The reaction being a cation-anion reaction is facilitated by the lower micro polarity of the structured water at the interface. With increase in W , the micro polarity increases resulting in decrease in rate. At the same time, with increasing W , the ionic strength decreases and therefore k_2 should increase because lower ionic strength favours a cation-anion reaction. In the case of ionic surfactants, the value of W regulates the concentrations of (CTA⁺) polar heads of the surfactant and its counter ions (Br⁻) in the aqueous water pool and therefore W gives the value of ionic strength (μ)⁹. For example, at $W = 5.61$, $[\text{Br}^-]_e = \mu$ and $[\text{Br}^-]_e = [\text{Br}^-]_o/f = 0.1/0.01009 = 9.91 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. For a change in W from 0.870 to 25.0 the ionic strength ($= [\text{Br}^-]_e$) changes from 63.8 mol dm^{-3} to 2.22 mol dm^{-3} . These values are given in Table 2. The combined effect of these two factors results in a small overall increase in k_2 indicating a slight predominance of ionic strength effect over polarity effect.

At higher W ($W = 10.0$ to 25.0), the increase in k_2 is much more pronounced. In this range, the special properties of water are attenuated and thus polarity effect on k_2 is not significant. The acceleration of the reaction is due to decrease in ionic strength with increase in W . Under these conditions, the reaction can be considered to have two components, one at the interface and other in the water pool. With increase in W , the latter component becomes increasingly important¹⁰. At high W ($W > 10$) the entrapped water behaves like bulk water and assuming that only ionic strength effect is present, the authors tried to assess the effect of W in terms of ionic strength relating the rate constant k_2 ,

$$k_2 = k_2^0 \frac{\gamma_{\text{HA}^-} \gamma_{\text{MB}^+}}{\gamma_{\#}} \quad (1)$$

where γ_{HA^-} , γ_{MB^+} and $\gamma_{\#}$ are the activity coefficients of HA⁻, MB⁺ and the transition state and k_2^0 is the rate constant at zero ionic strength. According to Guggenheim equation¹¹, the activity coefficient γ_i of an ion is related to ionic strength (μ)

$$-\log \gamma_i = \frac{AZ_i^2 \mu^{1/2}}{1 + \mu^{1/2}} - \sum_j B_{i,j} C_j \quad (2)$$

where A is equal to 0.5, Z_i is the charge on the ions and

the summation extending over all ions of concentration C_j . In the present case, the relevant specific interactions are between positively charged micellar surface (M) and HA⁻ and MB⁺ and Br⁻ represented respectively by the specific interaction terms $B_{\text{M,HA}^-}$, $B_{\text{MB}^+, \text{Br}^-}$. The specific interactions between ions whose concentrations are very small compared to the concentration of Br⁻ have been neglected. Using eqs. (1) and (2), it can be shown that

$$\log k_2 = \log k_2^0 - \frac{A\mu^{1/2}}{1 + \mu^{1/2}} + B_{\text{M,HA}^-} [\text{M}]_e + B_{\text{MB}^+, \text{Br}^-} [\text{Br}^-] \quad (3)$$

$[\text{M}]_e$ is equal to $[\text{CTAB}]_e/N$ where N is the aggregation number and $[\text{CTAB}]_e$ is equal to $[\text{Br}^-]_e$ since the source of Br⁻ is only CTAB.

$$\log k_2 = \log k_2^0 - \frac{A\mu^{1/2}}{1 + \mu^{1/2}} + B_{\text{M,HA}^-} \{[\text{Br}^-]_e/N\} + B_{\text{MB}^+, \text{Br}^-} [\text{Br}^-]_e \quad (4)$$

$$\log k_2 = \log k_2^0 - \frac{A\mu^{1/2}}{1 + \mu^{1/2}} + b[\text{Br}^-]_e \quad (5)$$

where $b = (B_{\text{M,HA}^-}/N) + (B_{\text{MB}^+, \text{Br}^-})$

The ionic strength of the water pool at $W = 5.61$ has been calculated to be 9.91 mol dm^{-3} and at $W = 25.0$ has a value of 2.22 mol dm^{-3} . It is known that at high ionic strengths, variation of the second term in the eq. (2) with μ can be neglected in comparison with the third term⁹. If this is true a plot of $\log k_2$ versus $[\text{Br}^-]_e$ should be linear. Interestingly, the Guggenheim plots are linear and parallel to each other for data repeated at different $[\text{CTAB}]$ (Fig. 1) and the specific interaction effect is included in the value of 'b' in eq. (5) which is equal to the slope of plot between $\log k_2$ and $[\text{Br}^-]_e$. The value of 'b' was found to be -0.105 , -0.104 and -0.108 for 0.1, 0.2 and 0.3 mol dm^{-3} CTAB respectively. Since there is a $[\text{CTAB}]$ effect on rate even at $W = 25.0$, it indicates the presence of reaction component both at interface and water pool and therefore the value of 'b' includes the interaction effect of both the interface and water pool components.

Effect of CTAB :

With increase in CTAB concentrations at constant W , the second order rate constant increases. This study has

Fig. 1. Effect of ionic strength on reduction of methylene blue by ascorbic acid.

been carried out in a detailed manner at low W (5.61) where the entrapped water is highly structured and is associated with lower micro polarity compared to bulk water. It has been reported that the berezin pseudo phase model is applicable to reactions taking place in reverse micellar media¹² and according to this model, the second order rate constant k_2 is given by,

$$k_2 = \frac{k_m P_{HA^-} P_{MB^+} C \bar{V} + k_w (1 - C \bar{V})}{(1 + K_{HA^-} C)(1 + K_{MB^+} C)} \quad (6)$$

$$k_2 = \frac{k_m P_{HA^-} K_{MB^+} C + k_w (1 - C \bar{V})}{(1 + K_{HA^-} C)(1 + K_{MB^+} C)} \quad (7)$$

In the above equation, k_m is the rate constant of the reaction at the interface, k_w is the rate constant of the entrapped water, C is the [CTAB] surfactant, V is the molar volume of surfactant. P_{HA^-} , P_{MB^+} are the partition coefficients of ascorbic acid and methylene blue. K_{MB^+} , K_{HA^-} are the binding constants of methylene blue, ascorbic acid and $K_{MB^+} = P_{MB^+} V$, and $K_{HA^-} = P_{HA^-} V$.

Neglecting $C.V$ in comparison to 1 and if $1 \gg (K_{HA^-}).C, (K_{MB^+}).C$, the above equation become

$$k_2 = K_m P_{HA^-} K_{MB^+} C + k_w \quad (8)$$

In the present case a plot of k_2 vs $[CTAB]_0$ is linear with a positive intercept (Fig. 2) giving evidences to the assumption that $1 \gg (K_{HA^-}).C, (K_{MB^+}).C$. The slope corresponding to $k_m P_{HA^-} K_{MB^+}$ and intercept gives the rate constant k_w for the reaction in the entrapped water. The value of k_w ($0.0360 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) is about 60 greater

Fig. 2. Effect of $[CTAB]_0$ at different $W = 5.61, 25.0$ on the reduction of methylene blue by ascorbic acid.

than the rate constant of the reaction in aqueous medium in the absence of surfactant ($k_0 = 5.33 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and bromide ion. The value of k_0 should have been much smaller at this ionic strength i.e. at $\mu = 9.91 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $W = 5.61$ but this high ionic strength cannot be achieved in aqueous medium to determine the value of k_0 under identical conditions. This large increase of rate in the reverse micelles illustrates the special properties of entrapped water i.e. micro polarity at low W 's. The berezin pseudo phase model has been applied to the data corresponding to higher W also ($W = 25.0$) and the plot of k_2 vs $[CTAB]_0$ is linear with a positive intercept. The value of k_w ($0.215 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) is very near to the rate constant of the reaction in aqueous medium at the same ionic strength in the absence of surfactant, k_0 ($0.290 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$). This shows the properties of the entrapped water at $W = 25.0$ are very near to that of the bulk water in the aqueous medium.

Spectral studies :

There is a decrease in absorbance for HA^- and MB^+ as [CTAB] is increased (Figs. 3, 4). The decrease in absorbance implies greater binding of both the reactants at the micellar surface and greater binding implies greater k_2 . The effect is more pronounced in the case of HA^- compared to MB^+ . This is quite understandable because MB^+ is cationic and binding takes place only due to hydrophobic interactions whereas in the case of HA^- the binding is favoured by the cationic surface.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of analytical reagent grade

Fig. 3. Spectra of ascorbic acid at different $[CTAB]_0$ at $W = 25.0$, $[HA^-]_0 = 1.1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Fig. 4. Spectra of methylene blue at different $[CTAB]_0$ at $W = 25.0$, $[MB^+]_0 = 1.4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

and solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. Methylene blue (MB) and ascorbic acid (H_2A) were purchased from Aldrich and were used as received. Stock solutions of methylene blue (MB) $6.36 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and ascorbic acid (H_2A) 0.6 mol dm^{-3} were prepared by dissolving the appropriate amounts of these compounds in doubly distilled water. Cetyl tri methyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) received from Merck (India) was used without further purification. Hexane and chloroform were distilled before use. A 0.1 mol dm^{-3} solution of CTAB was prepared by dissolving appropriate of CTAB in a chloroform-hexane (3 : 2 v/v) mixture.

Preparation of the reverse micellar system and initiation of the reaction :

A typical experiment was carried out as follows : Small

quantities of aqueous solutions of methylene blue (0.022 ml) were injected into 10 ml of CTAB solution using a micro pipette. Ascorbic acid (0.025 ml) was then added to initiate the reaction. These mixtures were shaken sufficiently to obtain a transparent and apparently homogeneous solution that can be regarded as a reverse micellar system. In all the experiments the molar ratio of [water] to [CTAB] i.e. W was varied in the range 0.870 to 25.0 (corresponding 0.047–0.450 ml of water).

Kinetic measurements :

Although the reverse micellar systems are heterogeneous on molecular scale they are macroscopically homogeneous and isotropic. Since they are optically transparent, a change in the concentration of the reactant/product can be followed by spectrophotometric method. The reduction kinetics of methylene blue (MB^+) with ascorbic acid (HA^-) was carried out under pseudo-first order conditions, $[HA^-] \gg [MB^+]$ by taking the initial concentrations of methylene blue as $1.4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and ascorbic in the range $0.1 \times 10^{-3} - 2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ respectively. The reactions were monitored by measuring the decrease in absorbance of MB^+ at 657.40 nm using Shimadzu UV-1800 spectrophotometer. The temperature 29°C was maintained in the reaction cell of the spectrophotometer by water circulating thermostatic bath. The observed first order rate constants (k_1) were calculated by a linear least-squares method from the relationship $\log(A_t - A_\infty)$ vs time. The kinetic data are the averages from triplicate runs with reproducibility of $\pm 5\%$.

Calculation of the effective concentrations in reverse micelles :

In the studies of reactions in reverse micelles involving water-soluble reactants, the reactivity in the aqueous droplets of the reverse micelle is usually compared with that in bulk aqueous medium. In the case of first order reactions the measured rate constants may be compared directly in the two types of systems. However, in the case of bimolecular processes, the calculation of the second order constant involves consideration of the concentration of species in the reverse micelle and the question arises as to whether the overall concentration or the concentration in the entrapped water i.e. the effective concentration should be employed. In the present reaction, the reduction of methylene blue by ascorbic acid has been

investigated in neutral medium. In neutral medium, the negatively charged species of ascorbic acid, HA^- is the dominant species ($pK_{a1} = 4.17$, $pK_{a2} = 11.57$)¹³. Since both the reactants, i.e. HA^- and MB^+ are ionic, they cannot exist in the oil phase but constrained only to the solubilised water. Therefore, their effective concentrations are to be considered for calculation of k_2 . For the calculation of second order rate constant, the effective concentration of a reactant in the water pool is calculated by dividing the overall concentration by the volume fraction of solubilised water, f (=Volume of aqueous phase/Total volume of the solution)¹⁴. The volume fractions lie in the range $(4.70\text{--}45.0) \times 10^{-3}$ for 0.1 mol dm^{-3} CTAB. Hence there is (212.7–22.20) fold increase in concentrations. For example, if the concentration of CTAB is 0.1 mol dm^{-3} , $W = 4.61$, $f = (0.083/10)$ and $[\text{HA}^-]_{\text{overall}} = 1.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ then $[\text{HA}^-]_{\text{effective}} = \{[\text{HA}^-]_{\text{overall}}/f\} = \{1.5 \times 10^{-3}/0.0083\} = 0.181 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. From now onwards, the subscript 'o' is used to represent overall concentrations and subscript 'e' to represent effective concentrations.

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